

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Extreme weather conditions interfere with agricultural field experiments

Extreme weather conditions (droughts, floods, severe storms) present significant challenges for agricultural field experiments as they disrupt carefully planned studies, affecting crop growth, soil conditions, and data collection. They not only compromise the integrity of the research, they also impact the reliability of results. A field experiment was maintained during 2019 till 2023 in Flanders, Belgium, known for its temperate climate. It aimed at exploring to what extent new strategies (application of farm yard manure, whether or not co-composted with

'brow' material, and a differential management of the cover crops (incorporation or mowing)) might maintain soil quality, sufficient crop yield and nitrogen supplying capacity. However, the mean temperature in 2020 was the highest ever recorded since 1991 and the number of tropical heat days and rainy days was extremely high and low respectively. As a result, the potato yield that year was low (<35000 kg/ha while a yield of >40000 kg/ha in Flanders is normal) and the valuable drawing of recommendations jeopardised.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Long-term field experiments or innovative strategies can avoid or mitigate extreme weather effects

European project calls should include more long-term proposals to provide the opportunity to organise and maintain field experiments during several 'climatological normal' cropping cycles. Researchers should be aware and account for weather-

related variables or try to mitigate extreme weather effects applying innovative strategies like large shelters, resilient crops, computer-driven large scale irrigation systems, etc.

1. Potato yield per treatment. (whiskers represent standard deviation). nAFV = cover crop destroyed and incorporated, AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, none = no organic fertilizer applied, FYM = farm yard manure added, FYMco = FYM co-composted with straw added (ILVO).

2. Hydrology, Drones & RAINout Shelters (HYDRAS). Een state-of-the-art installation for field experiments under drought-controlled conditions (ILVO).

KEYWORDS

Extreme weather, long-term field experiments, mitigation, potato crop yield

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